

Status of Co-curricular Activities in Secondary Schools during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Balasore District

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Abstract: Education is the process of unfolding an individual's inherent powers and potentialities. However, it can not be achieved through classroom teaching-learning process only. The co-curricular activities in the school environment play a significant role in the harmonious development of an individual. During COVID-19 pandemic, the classroom learning process was being conducted through virtual mode only, which also affected the conduction of co-curricular activities through physical mode in the school environment. The purpose of the study was to explore how co-curricular activities have been conducted in secondary schools amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, taking into account the factors of gender and location of the school. The descriptive survey method of research was used to carry out the study and the data was collected from 100 class - X students studying in government schools of two Blocks of Balasore district, Odisha. The study revealed that secondary-level students participated in co-curricular activities to a modest extent, with Female participating in co-curricular activities to a greater extent than Male. Once more, it was discovered that students from schools in urban regions and students from schools in rural areas both had comparable levels of participation.

IndexTerms: Co-curricular activities, COVID-19 Pandemic, school environment, gender, and locality

1. INTRODUCTION:

Education entails the systematic process of acquiring knowledge, experience, skills and a proper attitude for children and adults. One of the basic objectives of education, which is also known as harmonized development relates to the evolution of human beings' personalities, in terms of their physical, intellectual, emotional, spiritual, moral and aesthetic aspects. Harmonized development entails the education of the 3 H's i.e. Head, Heart and Hand. A wider range and ideal environment for their development may be provided by participating in co-curricular activities at school. Co-curricular activities are the activities conducted by the schools besides classroom learning to enhance various skills of the students and prepare them for the future aspect of their life. It may be possible to develop the child's personality traits such as leadership, tolerance, sociability, emotional maturity, problem-solving skills, and the capacity to give and obey through various co-curricular activities.

Figure – 1: Skills Developed through Co-Curricular Activities

Additionally, it is very challenging to define co-curricular activities because they go by a variety of names, including extra-curricular activities, extra-curricular class activities, non-class activities, etc. Co-curricular activities play a significant role in contemporary education. Activities at school like debates, dramatic literature, clubs, social service projects, gardening, photography, scouting and guiding, excursions, and any other events not listed on the regular school schedule are not considered co-curricular. However, these activities are now accepted as a component of the regular curriculum.

Figure – 2: Types of Co-curricular Activities Conducted in Schools

2. MOTIVATION GROUNDED FOR THE STUDY:

Co-curricular activities play an important component in the smooth operation of an educational institution. These activities enable the pupils to emerge as strong and sturdy younger humans of their state. Co-curricular activities are an activity wherein the students can express their feelings. The organizer wants to have the energy to bring cohesion and the sensation of oneness with every difference. But many schools no longer have the right region for engaging in those sports. At this juncture, there can be a need to check these elements so one can have an in-depth sight of the splendid co-curricular activities undertaken in the schools or not. In this pandemic, it is very difficult to conduct study room coaching-getting to know techniques in bodily mode. So we adopt a virtual mode of the analyzing system. In this example, the co-curricular sports activities of students are getting disregarded. As a result of which students are handling numerous problems like tension, melancholy, strain, weight troubles, and so on. So this look is based absolutely on the repute of co-curricular activities in secondary schools within the Balasore district of Odisha in terms of gender, and school locality.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The present study is concerned with the following objective identified by the investigators:

To study the participation status of co-curricular activities conducted in secondary schools during the COVID-19 pandemic with reference to the factors of gender and location.

4. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between male and female students of secondary schools in their participation in the co-curricular activities conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students in their participation in co-curricular activities during the COVID-19 pandemic.

5. METHODOLOGY:

The present study was conducted by employing a research design that is descriptive in nature. The purpose of employing this design was to systematically obtain information to describe the status of participation of students in various co-curricular activities during the COVID 19 pandemic.

5.1. Population of the study: The entire population for this study comprised Class X secondary school students in Balasore District, Odisha.

5.2. Sampling techniques: A sampling frame consisting of all the secondary schools of Balasore Sadar and Remuna Block were prepared by the researcher from the population by stratified random sampling. Out of 17 schools from Remuna Block (rural) and 36 schools of Sadar Block (urban), 3 & 2 schools were chosen respectively on simple random sampling techniques.

5.3. Sample for the study: Out of the overall population, a sample of 100 Class X students attending government schools in both the Balasore Sadar Block and Remuna Block was selected for the current study.

The researchers divided this sample into two groups: 74 students from urban areas (35 Male and 39 Female) and 26 students from rural areas (11 Male and 15 Female) to form the study's sample.

6. TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY:

In this study the investigators used a self-made tool i.e a questionnaire on co-curricular activities to collect the required data.

6.1. Construction of the tool: The investigators developed a questionnaire to assess the participation status of secondary school students in co-curricular activities. The initial draft of the Co-curricular Activities Questionnaire was created after a comprehensive review of relevant literature on co-curricular activities. This review involved an analysis of the attributes and components related to co-curricular activities, as developed by Sangma in 2012. Additionally, experts in the fields of psychology and education were consulted to ensure the content validity of the questionnaire. Their valuable input and suggestions were carefully considered.

Items in the questionnaire that were deemed ambiguous, doubtful, irrelevant, or defective were eliminated by the investigator in collaboration with the supervising teacher. After careful consideration of all these factors, the final version of the questionnaire was prepared, containing a total of 20 items.

6.2. Reliability & Validity of the Co-Curricular Activities Questionnaire: Content validity of the questionnaire was established by systematically analyzing the components under study, on the basis of the opinion of experts from relevant fields, it was ensured that the tool has sufficient coverage of its content. In the present study, the reliability coefficient of 0.83 was determined through a pilot study. Thus, the Co-curricular Activities questionnaire as a whole was considered a reasonably valid and reliable instrument for the the present investigation.

7. DATA COLLECTION TECHNIQUES:

The permission was obtained by the investigators from the school headmasters and they personally visited to the class rooms with maintaining proper Covid-19 protocol and distributed the questionnaires among the students. Following the distribution of the tool, students were briefed about the study's objectives. The administration of the questionnaire took approximately 20 to 30 minutes in each school.

7.1 Procedure adopted for scoring:

Scoring was based on a scale where choosing the option indicating poor received a score of zero, and choosing the option indicating high received a score of two. This scoring method allowed for a possible score range of 0 to 20 on the Co-curricular Activities Questionnaire.

8. DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES:

The collected data was analysed with the help of relevant statistical methods like percentage analysis and the t-test, to know the status of co-curricular activities conducted during COVID-19 Pandemic in Balasore District.

8.1 Analysis and Interpretation:**Table-1: Percentage Analysis of Male and Female Secondary School Students' Participation Status During the COVID-19 Pandemic**

Sl. No.	Co-curricular Activities	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
1	Dancing	7	20	27	25.93%	74.07%
2	Singing	7	12	19	36.85%	63.15%
3	Poem Recitation	0	4	4	0%	100%
4	Painting	7	32	39	17.95%	82.05%
5	Rangoli	0	7	7	0%	100%
6	Crafts	3	17	20	15%	85%
7	Acting	5	7	12	41.67%	58.33%
8	Essay Writing	23	34	57	40.35%	59.65%
9	Yoga	1	2	3	33.33%	66.67%
10	Gita Chanting	0	2	2	0%	100%
11	Tree Plantation	6	16	22	27.27%	72.73%
12	Musical Instruments	3	6	9	33.33%	66.67%
13	Games and Sports	23	18	41	56.10%	43.90%
14	Debate	22	23	45	48.89%	51.11%
15	G.K.	9	13	22	40.90%	59.10%
16	Local Trip	0	0	0	0%	0%
17	Red Cross	0	0	0	0%	0%
18	Wall Magazine	0	0	0	0%	0%
19	Educational Trip	0	0	0	0%	0%
20	Sanitation	46	54	100	46%	54%

Based on the student response during Pandemic, the participation percentages for Male and Female in various co-curricular activities are as follows: Male participated in events such as Dancing (25.93%), Singing (36.85%), Painting(17.95%), Crafts(15%), Yoga(33.33%), Tree Plantation(27.27%), Musical Instrument(33.33%) is less in Co-Curricular activity, Most of them participated in events such as Acting (41.67%), Games&Sports (56.10%), G.K (40.90%) debate (48.89%). None of the Male participated in Events

like Local Trip, Red Cross, Wall Magazine, Educational Trip, Poem recitation, Rangoli, and Gita Chanting. However, all of them participated in Sanitation activities.

Whereas, the Female participated in events such as Dancing (74.07%), Painting (82.05%), Crafts (85%), Tree Plantation (72.73%), majority percentage, Singing (63.85%), Acting (58.33%), Essay Writing (59.65%), Musical Instrument (66.66%), Yoga (66.67%), Games & Sports (43.90), Debate (51.11%), G.K. (59.10%), Most percent participation in co-curricular activities, None or Zero Participation of Female in Events like Local Trip, Red Cross, Wall Magazine, Educational Trip, All Participate in Poem recitation, Rangoli, Gita Chanting.

Figure- 3: Participation in various co-curricular activities based on Gender

Table 2: Percentage Analysis of Urban and Rural Secondary School Students' Participation Status During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Sl. No.	Co-curricular Activities	Urban	Rural	Total	Urban %	Rural %
1	Dancing	17	10	27	62.96%	37.03%
2	Singing	10	9	19	52.63%	47.36%
3	Poem Recitation	2	2	4	50%	50%
4	Painting	26	13	39	66.66%	33.33%
5	Rangoli	5	2	7	71.42%	28.57%
6	Crafts	13	7	20	65%	35%
7	Acting	7	5	12	58.33%	41.66%
8	Essay Writing	38	19	57	66.66%	33.33%
9	Yoga	2	1	3	66.66%	33.33%

10	Gita Chanting	0	2	2	0%	100%
11	Tree Plantation	21	1	22	95.45%	4.54%
12	Musical Instruments	9	0	9	100%	0%
13	Games and Sports	25	16	41	60.97%	39.02%
14	Debate	29	16	45	64.44%	35.55%
15	G.K.	18	4	22	81.81%	18.18%
16	Local Trip	0	0	0	0%	0%
17	Red Cross	0	0	0	0%	0%
18	Wall Magazine	0	0	0	0%	0%
19	Educational Trip	0	0	0	0%	0%
20	Sanitation	54	46	100	54%	46%

Based on the student response during the pandemic, The participation Percent for Urban and Rural areas in co-curricular activities are as follows: In urban areas co-curricular activities such as Dancing (62.96%), Singing (50%) Painting (66.66%), Crafts 965%), Acting (58.33%), Both in Essay writing and Yoga (66.66%), Games & Sports (60.97%) and Debate (64.44%), Majority participate in G.K (81.81%), Tree Plantation (95.45%), Rangoli (71.42%).None of the urban students participated in Events like Local Trip, Red Cross, Wall Magazine, Educational Trip. Gita Chanting, All participate in Musical Instruments.

Whereas, in Rural area the percentage of participation in co-curricular activities such as Dancing (37.03%), Painting (33.33%), Rangoli (28.57%), Crafts (35%), Both in Essay writing and Yoga (33.33%), Tree Plantation (4.54%), Games & Sports (39.02%) and debate (35.55%), G.K (18.18%). Sanitation (46%), most percent participation in events such as Singing (47.36%), Poem Recitation (50%), Acting (41.66%). None of them Participate in Events like Local Trip, Red Cross, Wall Magazine, Educational Trip Musical Instruments, All participate in Gita Chanting.

Figure- 4: Participation in various co-curricular activities based on locality

Table 3: Test of Significance of Difference between Mean Participation Scores of Male and Female Students in Co-Curricular Activities

Sub sample	N	M	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Male	46	3.70	2.10	2.50	t>0.05
Female	54	4.80	2.26		

Table 3 demonstrates a statistically significant "t"-value of 2.50 when comparing male and female secondary school students' participation in co-curricular activities during the pandemic period, at a significance level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis (Ho1) – which posited that there was no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in their participation in co-curricular activities conducted during the COVID–19 pandemic – was rejected. This rejection implies that a significant difference indeed exists between male and female secondary school students in their participation in co-curricular activities.

As indicated in the table, the mean participation score for male students is 3.70, whereas for female students, it is 4.80. This suggests that female students' participation in co-curricular activities is higher than that of their male counterparts.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Difference between Mean Participation Scores of Urban and Rural Students in Co-Curricular Activities

Category	N	M	SD	t-value	Level of significance
Urban	74	4.19	1.93	0.75	t > 0.05
Rural	26	4.58	3.0		

Table 4 presents a "t"-value of 0.75 when comparing participation in co-curricular activities between urban secondary school students and their rural counterparts. This value was not found to be statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level, with the critical value being 1.95. Consequently, the null hypothesis (i.e., Ho₂) was not rejected. The means of the two groups are 4.19 and 4.58, respectively, indicating that the mean participation score of students from urban schools is similar to that of students from rural schools. Therefore, it can be concluded that students from schools located in urban areas exhibit a comparable level of participation in co-curricular activities to students from schools in rural areas.

10. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Owing to the Covid-19 Pandemic, curriculum was delivered virtually and through a mixed learning environment for an extended period of time. Pandemic also severely impacted the participation of students in co-curricular activities. Learning gaps in cognitive, physical, social, and emotional domains resulted from the closing of the school. As a result of which the following results are founded by the researcher

1. The participation in co-curricular activities among secondary-level students was observed to be at a moderate level. To enhance participation and promote awareness about the importance and benefits of engaging in co-curricular activities, it is recommended to organize seminars, conferences, and workshops specifically tailored for secondary-level students.
2. When it comes to involvement in sports and games, male students demonstrated higher participation than their female counterparts. It is crucial to recognize that both physical and mental health are influenced by active participation in sports and activities. To encourage greater involvement of female students in sports and games, it is essential to provide them with proper guidance and suitable facilities, which will help increase their active engagement in these activities.
3. The study reveals that participation in co-curricular activities positively develops the personality in terms of appearance, verbal mannerisms, gesticulation stability of thoughts, leadership skills, and self-confidence of secondary-level students. In light of these findings, it is recommended that teachers identify students lacking these qualities and encourage their participation in co-curricular activities. This proactive approach can assist secondary school students in enhancing dimensions of their personality where improvements are needed.

4. It's important for teachers to be well-informed about the nature of co-curricular activities conducted in schools and actively monitor their students' involvement in these activities. Active participation is crucial for the development of students' personalities and decision-making skills.
5. Parents should not focus solely on their children's academic achievements but should also recognize the importance of their all-round development. It is essential for parents to encourage and provide opportunities for their children to engage in co-curricular activities to ensure their holistic growth. To facilitate this, parents should be educated about the significance of co-curricular activities.

11. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, co-curricular activities play a significant role in contemporary education by contributing to the comprehensive development of students. School activities such as debates, drama, literary clubs, social service projects, gardening, photography, scouting and guiding, excursions, and various other events that fall outside the standard curriculum are essential components of co-curricular activities. These activities have the potential to enhance the joy of learning and are a crucial motivation for effective teaching and learning. A successful teaching and learning process can be achieved when there is a seamless integration of the curriculum with co-curricular activities.

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